

Criteria and indicators for the certification of the sustainable management of an agroforestry system PEFC

Introduction

Since November 2020, the Programme for Endorsement of Forest Certification schemes - PEFC Italy - has been on a path to develop a certification standard for the sustainable management of agroforestry systems. During the NEWTON project a working group with a large number of stakeholders from the agroforestry sector was established; in the spring of 2022, the PEFC national standard was created and in the summer of 2022 three pilot tests were carried out in the NEWTON project partner companies. The PEFC analysis had as objectives the study of the tools and standards for guaranteeing the traceability and sustainability of agroforestry production and the related products processed by the project partner companies. This studies were followed by an analysis of the type of certifiable products derived from the agricultural, livestock, forestry and agroforestry components of these products. During the pilot tests conducted with the company's technicians, it was possible to concretely analyse in the field the guidelines and indicators established during the standard drafting process, highlighting the difficult application of some and improving others. The main results obtained in the study carried out in the partner companies saw the identification of 48 products (or product categories) and 13 processed and manufactured products; these 61 products are potentially subject to certification, some of them with more than 35 different schemes of environmental and quality certification schemes worldwide. Thanks to the cooperation of the project partners, the document 'Criteria and indicators for the certification of the sustainable management of an agroforestry system PEFC ' was produced, the first European-wide certification standard for the tree component of an agroforestry system, available from 2023, to valorise local agroforestry products.

Lessons learned

According to the PEFC Italia scheme, the certification of the sustainable management of an agroforestry system allows access to the market with product and system traceability certifications to give the end consumer a guarantee of the correct management of the company system.

The experiences and knowledge gained during the project will be taken as an example by others in the regional and national scene, and for the project partner companies it will be a document already known and easily implemented for the certification of products resulting from sustainable agroforestry management.

The standard allows companies to certify their sustainable management and can be used as a marketing and communication tool for the products, enhancing a company marketing that is more prudent and respectful of environmental requirements, thus implementing farm sustainability in social and environmental terms.

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The information presented in this factsheet was developed by the FOREST4EU partner, drawing on the innovations and knowledge generated by the indicated operational group with their explicit authorization.

Further information

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